

Mobile cart with head only electric stunning device, for on farm culling and carcass collection

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Introduction

Cervical dislocation is the most common on farm method used for emergency killing of sick or injured birds. However, there is evidence that cervical dislocation may not always induce immediate loss of consciousness. For this reason, several animal welfare assessment schemes propose, as gold standard, to stun the birds by percussive blow followed by cervical dislocation as a killing method. However, also percussive blow may not consistently induce unconsciousness and requires that personnel performing this method is properly trained to stun the birds consistently, humanely, and effectively.

According to Reg. 1099/2009, cervical dislocation and percussive blow to the head shall only be used on poultry up to 5 kg live weight and, in case of manual cervical dislocation, shall not be used on birds above three kg live weight. Furthermore, no person shall kill by manual cervical dislocation or percussive blow to the head more than seventy birds per day and the methods shall not be used as routine methods but only where no other methods are available (figure 1).

Figure 1: a) manual cervical dislocation, b) percussive blow, c) mechanical cervical dislocation, ©IZSLER)

Similarly to neck dislocation, percussive blow to the head is generally not well accepted by most operators.

For all these reasons, there is interest in identifying alternative stunning systems that can be shared as good practices.

Electrical stunning is recognized as a humane method for stunning poultry.

The method in general consists in passing a current through the head of the bird to induce a seizure which causes an instantaneous loss of consciousness.

In particular, head-only stunning systems perform individual stunning and when correctly operated, are able to consistently induce instantaneous loss of consciousness (figure 2).

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Figure 2: head-only electrical stunning

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An electrical cart equipped with a head only electrical stunner has been adopted in some farms to improve the welfare of birds during culling operations.

The cart can be successfully used during the daily inspections both for the collection of dead birds as well as the culling of birds experiencing pain and the subsequent transfer of the carcasses to the disposal area.

During inspections, the speed of the cart can be adapted to the operator's requirements and is equipped with 3 containers for carcass collection with a total capacity of 100kg.

The stunning device is attached to the rear of the cart and has been designed and manufactured in compliance with Reg 1009/2009. It has fixed tongues that hold electrodes, with which the animals can be stunned before being killed through bleeding, induced by mechanical cervical dislocation with the use of a purposely designed device (hook) attached to the cart (figure 3).

Figure 3: Hook for mechanical cervical dislocation.

Current regulation: it is possible to process birds of different size, species, and category such as pigeons, broilers and layer chickens, ducks, geese, turkeys etc.

The control panel (figure 4), equipped with convenient drive devices and a large display, allows the operator to easily adjust the machine parameters and read the information quickly and clearly.

Figure 4: Control panel of the device.

The USB connector integrated (figure 5) into the electronic equipment automatically records the stunning data (date – time – Ampere – Volt – Hertz – Seconds) in the USB key, without the need for operator intervention. The frequency is fixed at 50 Hz, while the voltage will vary according to the settings based on the resistance of the bird processed.

Figure 5: Control panel of the device.

Once the birds head (figure 6) is introduced between the tongues of the stunner, its impedance is detected and the necessary voltage to ensure the correct current flow is delivered to the bird by pressing the button. Exposure time can be set according to legislation requirements and an acoustic signal will indicate the correct exposure time. The efficacy of stunning can be detected by the operator who will then immediately complete the killing of the bird by mechanical neck dislocation. Exsanguination, through mechanical cervical dislocation, to achieve death should be performed within 15 seconds after stunning.

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Dislocation is done mechanically by placing the bird's neck in the hook attached to the cart and pulling the birds legs upwards towards the operator. Successful dislocation can be assessed by feeling the gap between the bird's head and its neck. The bird is then placed in the container on the cart for disposal after the assessment of death indicators. Indicators of death are absence of palpebral reflex, absence of breathing and carcass relaxation.

Figure 6: Birds head is introduced between the tongues of the stunner.

Benefits of a mobile electrical cart

The stunning device, is easy to operate and when correctly used ensures an effective stun of birds belonging to different species and categories, avoiding limitations and uncertainties that are inherent to percussive stunning and neck dislocation. Mechanical neck dislocation applied within less than 15 seconds post stun is an effective means of killing through bleeding with no blood loss in the environment. Use of an electrical cart ensures proper and reduced handling, which is vital to minimise distress, particularly in the case of birds experiencing pain. An electrical cart equipped with a head only electrical stunner has the advantage of bringing the stunning device to the suffering bird avoiding the need to transport the bird to reach the stunner.

Figure 7: Suffering bird.

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Legal References

"All animals kept in husbandry systems in which their welfare depends on frequent human attention shall be inspected at least once a day" (Directive 98/58/EC, Annex, point 2).

"All chickens kept on the holding must be inspected at least twice a day. Special attention should be paid to signs indicating a reduced level of animal welfare and/or animal health"(Directive 2007/43/EC, Annex I, Paragraph 8).

"Any animal which appears ill or injured must be cared for appropriately without delay and, where an animal does not respond to such care, veterinary advice must be obtained as soon as possible" (Directive 98/58/EC, Annex, point 4).

"Chickens that are seriously injured or show evident signs of health disorder, such as those having difficulties in walking, severe ascites or severe malformations, and are likely to suffer, shall receive appropriate treatment or be culled immediately" (Directive 2007/43/EC, Annex I, Paragraph 9) (figure 7).

"It is an ethical duty to kill productive animals which are in severe pain where there is no economically viable way to alleviate such pain." (Reg. EC 1099/2009, preamble 12).

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